

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AND SELF-EFFICACY AMONG ADOLESCENTS

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ABSTRACT

The future of our nation lies in the hand of our younger generation but inadequacy and irrelevance of our existing education system has brought about a state of disillusionment among adolescents. Hence the current scenario is not very promising. Adolescents must know and practice the truth. There is the need of the qualitative as well as quantitative expansion and improvement of education. Our education must be modern in life and spirit. The main interest in an educational system is in academic achievement of child which is affected by numerous variables. Achievement motivation and self-efficacy are those factors which greatly influence the achievement of the children. Achievement motivation plays an important role in life. A little success motivates the individual to have something more in life. It leads towards higher aspirations and better performance. Self-efficacy affects every area of life. It is strength of one's belief in one's own ability to complete task and reach goals. A sample of 200 school students was randomly drawn from govt. and private schools located in Ferozepur. Insignificant difference has been found between achievement motivation of adolescent boys and girls. Significant difference has been found between self-efficacy among adolescent boys and girls. Self efficacy of girls was found to be significantly higher than that of boys. Significant positive relation was found between the variables i.e achievement motivation and self efficacy.

Introduction

Education is the basic tool for the development of the human being. Education occurs in a structured environment whose explicit purpose is teaching students. Education, in a very general sense can be summed up at a basic level as referring to an experience or act that has a formative effect on the mind, character or physical ability of an individual. Within the social and cultural context, education can be seen as the process by which society transmits its accumulated knowledge, values and skills from one generation to the next. In this sense, education is not only used to instil the values and norms of a given society, but is also an important element of the socialization process. Different forms of education have different structures of learning that define the learning process and what is seen as educational achievement.

Achievement motivation

Achievement motivation denotes processes leading to behaviour that aims to achieve a certain criterion or standard. The criterion can be any goal or objective, formal or informal, set by an individual or by others, in any professional or leisure domain which provides a guide for evaluating success and failure. This is the need for success or the attainment of excellence. Individuals will satisfy their need through different means and are driven to succeed for varying reasons both internal and external. These motivators are not inherent; we develop them through our culture and life experiences. It is a primary condition to achieve something. Achievement goals can affect the way a person performs a task and represent a desire to show competence. Ormrod (2004) defined one motivational construct-achievement motivation-as the need for excellence for its own sake, without regard for any external rewards that one's accomplishments might bring. Maehr (2008) defined that achievement motivation is largely social psychological in nature. It often occurs within groups, where interpersonal interactions can undermine or facilitate engagement in the tasks to be done. Gobari (2008) defined that achievement

motivation is one of the acquired motivations that sparked a lot of debate and controversy among educators and it is one of the inherent needs which are associated with the motivated plaudits of the individual.

Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy has become one of the important topics of research among psychologist and educators. The self-efficacy theory holds that the initiation persistence of particular behaviour and course of action is affected by people's belief about their behavioural capabilities and their like hood of coping with environmental challenges. Self-efficacy has been argued to be an important construct in the organizational science, often examined as an individual difference factor capable of influencing the relation between antecedents and consequences.

Self- efficacy is persons' belief in his or her ability to complete a future task or solve a future problem. Hodgesm (2008) said that self-efficacy is setting particular goals and fluctuates from situation to situation. Self-efficacy is subject to the space or the levels of task requests inside of which it is connected to and can't be measured through an omnibus test. Gavora (2010) defined self-efficacy as one's conviction about their capabilities to carry out certain tasks in a suitable and effective manner. Han, Liou-Mark, Yu and Zeng (2015) defined self-efficacy as one's belief or perception about one's capability to perform at a certain level on a task. Self-efficacy is the individual's conviction or confidence that they can successfully accomplish given tasks at designated level.

Need of the study

The future of our nation lies in the hand of our younger generation but inadequacy and irrelevance of our existing education system has brought about a state of disillusionment in the adolescents. Hence the current scenario is not very promising. Adolescents must know and practice the truth. There is the need of the qualitative as well as quantitative expansion and improvement of education. Our education must be modern in life and spirit. The main interest in an educational system is in

academic achievement of child which is affected by numerous variables. Achievement motivation and self-efficacy are those factors which greatly influence the achievement of the children. Achievement motivation plays an important role in life. A little success motivates the individual to have something more in life. It leads towards higher aspirations and better performance. Self-efficacy affects every area of life. It is strength of one's belief in one's own ability to complete task and reach goals.

Most of the studies revealed that achievement motivation was related to different variables such as academic achievement (Verkuyten, Thijs & Canatan, 2001; Bakar, Elias, Luan & Ayub, 2010; Awan, Noureen & Naz, 2011; Rashmi & Prasad, 2013; Herrero, 2014; Chetri, 2014; Kumari & Chamundeswari, 2015); home environment (Muola, 2010); attitude (Bakar, Elias, Luan & Ayub, 2010); and self-concept (Awan, Noureen & Naz, 2011); study habits (Kumari & Chamundeswari, 2015), hope (Herrero, 2014) and resilience (Herrero, 2014).

Most of the studies reviewed indicated that self-efficacy is related to different variables such as academic achievement (Zajacova, Lynch & Espenshade, 2005; Mahyuddin, Elias, Cheong, Muhamad, Noordin & Abdullah, 2006; Shkullaku, 2013; Goulao, 2014; Shkullaku, 2013; Tenaw, 2013 and Lilian, 2012), attitude (Rezaei & Miandashti, 2013), research anxiety (Rezaei & Miandashti, 2013) and burn out (Savas, Bozgeyik & Eser, 2014).

Only two studies were conducted so far to investigate relationship between achievement motivation and self efficacy (Zhang, Zhang, Zhang, Wang & Liu, 2015 and Birgani, Sahaghi & Moridi, 2016).

Not much research work has been done on the proposed topic in India. Investigator did not find any study conducted on the secondary school students of Punjab and Chandigarh. As the investigator did not find any study conducted on secondary school students which investigate the relationship between achievement motivation and self efficacy, the proposed study thus seems to be fully justified.

Objectives of the study

1. To investigate the significance of difference between means of achievement motivation of adolescent boys and girls.
2. To investigate the significance of difference between means of self-efficacy of adolescent boys and girls.
3. To investigate the relationship between achievement motivation and self-efficacy of adolescents.

Hypotheses of the study

1. There will be no significant difference in achievement motivation of adolescent boys and girls.
2. There will be no significant difference in self-efficacy of adolescent boys and girls.
3. There will be no significant relationship between achievement motivation and self-efficacy of adolescents.

Tools used

Achievement Motivation Scale by Dr. Gopal Rao

Self-Efficacy Scale by Dr .G. P. Mathur and Dr. Raj Kumari Bhatnagar

Sample of the study

A sample of 200 adolescents was randomly drawn from govt. and public secondary schools located in Ferozepur.

Statistical techniques used

Mean, Standard deviation, t-ratio and co-efficient of correlation were used for the analysis of data.

Delimitations

1. The present study is restricted to the schools of Ferozepur only.
2. The sample is delimited to 200 adolescents only.

3. In the present study, relationship is studied between two variables only i.e. achievement motivation and self-efficacy.

Analysis and interpretation of data

To give the authenticity and credibility to work of research, analysis and interpretation is always done in the light of objectives and hypotheses.

Hypothesis- I

There will be no significant difference in achievement motivation of adolescent boys and girls.

For this purpose 't' value between the mean scores of adolescent boys and girls was calculated.

Table-1: Showing the difference between the level of achievement motivation of adolescent boys and girls

Sr. No.	Category	N	Mean	S.D	't' Value	Level of significance
1	Boys	100	57.45	27.34	0.25	Insignificant at 0.05 and 0.01 level
2	Girls	100	58.45	28.23		

It is evident from the table that the t- value between the mean scores of boys and girls is 0.25 that is insignificant at both 0.05 and 0.01 levels. This shows that there is insignificant difference in achievement motivation of boys and girls. So, our hypothesis stands accepted.

Hypothesis II

There will be no significant difference between self-efficacy of adolescent boys and girls.

For this purpose 't' value between the mean scores of adolescent boys and girls was calculated.

Table-2: Showing difference in self-efficacy of adolescent boys and girls

Sr. No.	Category	N	Mean	S.D	't' value	Level of Significance
1	Boys	100	37.75	35.02	2.58	Significant at 0.05 level and equal at 0.01 level
2	Girls	100	53.15	48.22		

It is evident from the table that the t- value between the mean scores of boys and girls is 2.58 that is significant at 0.05 level and equal at 0.01 level. This shows that there is significant difference in self-efficacy of boys and girls. So, our hypothesis stands rejected.

Hypothesis III

There will be no significant relationship between achievement motivation and self-efficacy of adolescents.

For this purpose, the co-efficient of correlation was calculated by using Pearson Product moment method.

Table-3: Showing coefficient of correlation between achievement motivation and self-efficacy of adolescents

Sr. No.	Variables	N	r- value	Level of Significance
1	Achievement motivation	100	0.965	Significant at 0.05 level and insignificant at 0.01 level
2	Self-efficacy	100		

It is evident from the table that the r-value between achievement motivation and self-efficacy is found to be 0.965 that is significant at 0.05 level and insignificant at 0.01 levels. This shows that there is partial relationship between achievement motivation and self-efficacy of adolescents. So, our hypothesis stands partially accepted and partially rejected.

Findings of the study

1. The t- value between the mean scores of achievement motivation of adolescent boys and girls is 0.25 that is insignificant at both 0.05 and 0.01 levels. This shows that there is insignificant difference in achievement motivation of boys and girls.
2. The t- value between the mean scores of self-efficacy of adolescent boys and girls is 2.58 that is significant at 0.05 level and equal at 0.01 level. This shows that there is significant difference in self-efficacy of boys and girls.
3. The r-value between achievement motivation and self- efficacy is found to be 0.965 that is significant at 0.05 level and insignificant at 0.01 levels. This shows that there is partial relationship between achievement motivation and self-efficacy of adolescents.

Conclusions of the study

1. It was concluded that there was insignificant difference between achievement motivation of boys and girls indicating the fact that achievement motivation is not influenced by gender differences.
2. It was concluded that there was significant difference between self-efficacy among boys and girls. Self efficacy of girls was found to be significantly higher than that of boys.
3. The significant positive relation was found between the variables i.e. achievement motivation and self efficacy.

Educational Implications

The present study was designed to study relationship between achievement motivation and self-efficacy among adolescents. It was purposed to find out how far

the self-efficacy is related with achievement motivation and how far self-efficacy affects the level of achievement motivation among adolescents.

- To improve achievement motivation and self-efficacy the teacher should make healthy relationships with his students. He should use appropriate method of teaching and should also create better learning environment.
- Positive achievement motivation should be given by teachers and parents should understand the individual difference of the children. The teacher should give positive reinforcement and feedback. He should avoid false criticism. Student's self efficacy should also be raised by positive reinforcement.
- Students should realize their potentialities and capabilities. They should be aware of one's own life. They should make time table of routine works. Yoga practice, routine exercise should be helpful to maximize the self-efficacy.
- Proper co-curricular activities related to curriculum should be provided by the curriculum makers to maximize the self-efficacy among adolescents.
- Proper guidance should be provided to the students from time to time to solve their personal, educational and social problems.

References

- Awan, R. U. N., Noureen, G. & Naz, A.(2011). A study of relationship between achievement motivation, self-concept and achievement in English and Mathematics at secondary level. *International Educational Studies*, 4 (3). doi:10.5539/ies.v4n3p72
- Birgani ,S. A., Sahaghi, H. & Moridi, J.(2016).Relationship between achievement motivation, academic self-efficacy beliefs with academic performance among students of Jondishapour Medical Science University of Ahvaz. *International Journal of Current Research in Medical Sciences*, 89-93.
- Chetri, S. (2014). Achievement motivation of adolescents and its relationship with academic achievement. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 3(6), 8-15.

- Goulao, M. D. F. (2014). The relationship between self-efficacy and academic achievement in adults' learners. *Athens Journal of Education*, 237-246.
- Kumari, R. S. & Chamundeswari, S. (2015). Achievement motivation, study habits and academic achievement of students at the secondary level. *International Journal of Emerging Research in Management & Technology*, 4 (10), 7-13.
- Muola, J. M. (2010). A study of the relationship between academic achievement motivation and home environment among standard eight pupils. *Academic Journals Full Length Research Paper*, 5 (5), 213-217.
- Rezaei, M. & Miandashti, N. Z (2013). The relationship between research self-efficacy, research anxiety and attitude toward research: a study of agricultural graduate students. *Journal of Educational and Instructional Studies in the World*, 3, 69-78.
- Shkullaku, R. (2013). The relationship between self-efficacy and academic performance in the context of gender among Albanian students. *European academic research*, 1(4), 467-478. Available at <http://euacademic.org/UploadArticle/33.pdf>
- Tenaw, Y. A. (2013). Relationship between self-efficacy, academic achievement and gender in analytical Chemistry at Debre Markos college of teacher education. *AJCE*, 3(1), 3-28. Available at <http://www.ajol.info/index.php/ajce/article/viewFile/84850/74836>